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P	Public	X
C	Confidential, only for members of the consortium and the Commission Services	

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0.5	20/11/2019	Enzo Rotunno, Stefano Frabboni	CNR UMR	Review and comments
1.0	30/11/2019	Luca Marco Carlo Giberti Raffaella Santucci	QED QED	Final version integrating the comments of the peer reviewers and partners

Statement of originality:

This deliverable contains original unpublished work except where clearly indicated otherwise. Acknowledgement of previously published material and of the work of others has been made through appropriate citation, quotation or both.

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This deliverable describes the “*Making Open Science Work for you*” webinar. This is the sixth in the planned series of 9 Interdisciplinary Training Webinars for the Q-SORT project.

The Interdisciplinary Training Webinars are part of Work Package 3 **Theory, optical testing, and TEM implementation of generalised Sorter** [Months: 1-41], Task 3.5 - Interdisciplinary Training Webinars (M6, M11, M12, M18, M24, M26, M30, M36, M41).

This document is comprised of four Chapters, including Introduction and Conclusions.

The Introduction describes what a webinar is.

Chapter 2 summarises what we mean by Interdisciplinary Training Webinars and what their function is within Q-SORT.

Chapter 3 illustrates context, aims, and content of the fourth Interdisciplinary Training Webinar of Q-SORT.

The conclusions outline future plans for the Interdisciplinary Training Webinars.

1 INTRODUCTION - WHAT IS A WEBINAR?

A webinar is a web-based seminar which can be streamed either live or on demand. It might be just a simple audio stream, or it might include visual aids, such as PowerPoint slides, recorded video clips, or live software demonstrations.

The experience of a webinar attempts to reproduce the benefits of attending a seminar. Audience members can ask questions and the speaker can survey or poll the audience and get feedback as he or she delivers the information.

Webinar technology providers need to support these interactive elements in addition to the basic delivery of the audio and video streams. Keyboard chat features and Q&A are usually subject to more control, whereby the presenters can see messages from the audience and choose whether to broadcast them to all participants, ignore them, or reply privately.

The Q-SORT Interdisciplinary Webinars make use of Facebook Live as a platform for live streaming. We chose this platform as it provides the best value for money and offers the added advantage of being very widespread. Users are able to pose questions by posting comments below the video. Answers can be provided by specialists during or after the webinar.

2 THE Q-SORT INTERDISCIPLINARY TRAINING WEBINARS

The Q-SORT project is intrinsically interdisciplinary, being born from the cross-fertilisation of three subject areas: light optics (UG, MPI), electron microscopy (CNR, FZJ, UMR, FEI), and biology (MU).

The silo-breaking nature of Q-SORT provides added value through the following cross-fertilisation dynamics: microscopists borrow techniques from light optics specialists and in turn explain the challenges of the new measurements; biologists explain to physicists the problems that usually arise when studying proteins and suggest alternative proteins for investigation; physicists develop the quantum mechanical approach to cryo-TEM; biologists communicate a priori knowledge to light optics theoreticians in order to streamline efforts in the project work-packages (WP3-WP5).

In order to facilitate mutual learning between physicists and biologists, as well as to foster possible further applications to biology and the life sciences, 9 Q-SORT Interdisciplinary Training Webinars have been planned during the lifetime of the project. Their main aim is to function as aids to facilitate the highly interdisciplinary work in WP3 and in the other research WPs. They will do so by providing opportunities for training and mutual learning mentored by senior scientists, for forging a common language, for exchanging ideas for further joint research.

However important their role within Q-SORT, these seminars are meant to be accessible to everyone, hence the choice to propose them as webinars, so as to reach as wide an audience as possible.

The Interdisciplinary Training Webinars introduce a sort of 'intermediate level' in the communication of science: i.e. their nature is intermediate between the specialist-to-specialist character of discipline-specific communication tools -such as colloquia, talks, papers- and the broad appeal of conventional public understanding of science.

This is why, besides their facilitating function within WP3 and the other research WPs, the Interdisciplinary Training Webinars also play an important role in the dissemination and engagement process. Together with the Website, they ensure that Q-SORT will reach a broad range of pertinent audiences across Europe and beyond.

In the following paragraph we describe the fifth of the 9 Interdisciplinary Training Webinars planned for Q-SORT.

3 THE Q-SORT SIXTH INTERDISCIPLINARY TRAINING WEBINAR: MAKING OPEN SCIENCE WORK FOR YOU

Najla Retteberg, University of Gottingen (Germany) & Tim Smith, CERN (Switzerland)

02 July 2019, h. 4:30-5:15 PM CET

[Facebook Live: https://www.facebook.com/quantumsorter/](https://www.facebook.com/quantumsorter/)

<http://www.qsort.eu/making-open-science-work-for-you/>

This is a special webinar, marking the **collaboration between Q-SORT and CERN / OPENAIRE initiative**.

The “*Making Open Science Work for you*” *Interdisciplinary Training Webinar* was recorded and webcast on 02 July 2018, during the second [International Conference on Quantum Imaging and Beam Shaping](#) at Max Planck Institute for the Science of Light. The conference was organised by Q-SORT and the “[Science and Applications of Electron Wavefunctions Shaped and Manipulated by Engineered Nanoholograms](#)” DIP project (*Deutsch-Israelische Projekt cooperation grant*) with the support of the Max Planck Institute for the Science of Light and the [Nanoscience Institute of CNR \(CNR-NANO\)](#).

The webinar featured two of the conference invited speakers, **Najla Retteberg, University of Gottingen (Germany) & Tim Smith, CERN (Switzerland)**

The webinar totaled 32K views and 506 engagements (post clicks, likes, comments, shares, etc.). Facebook posts related to this webinar reached over 74K people.

The webinar was recorded with two cameras -one for the speaker, the other for the screen and the laser pointer-, then stored on remote servers for subsequent on-demand viewing.

The content of the Webinar was agreed upon by the Project Coordinator, Dr. Vincenzo Grillo (CNR) with Prof. Najla Retteberg, University of Gottingen (Germany) & Tim Smith, CERN (Switzerland), Dr. Luca Marco Carlo Giberti (QED) and Dr. Raffaella Santucci (QED)

The webinar can be re-watched on demand - interested parties can re-play it at their convenience by clicking on the following links:

on the Q-SORT website:

<http://www.qsort.eu/making-open-science-work-for-you/>

on Facebook:

<https://www.facebook.com/quantumsorter/videos/348730289152082/>

3.1 TECHNICAL DESCRIPTION

The sixth Q-SORT Interdisciplinary Training Webinar touches upon the following topics:

- Open Science;
- Zenodo;
- Open Access.

This is a Q-SORT outreach event in collaboration with [CERN](#), [Zenodo](#) and [OpenAIRE Advance](#)

Q-SORT established a collaboration with OpenAire Advance, CERN and ZENODO in an webinar on Open Science.

The webinar, “**Making Open Science Work for You**“, has been broadcasted on 2 July 2019. ([Facebook Live](#), <https://www.facebook.com/quantumsorter/>), as part of the [Q-SORT Conference on Quantum Imaging and Electron Beam Shaping](#).

The talk was presented by **Najla Retteberg (OpenAire Project, Goettingen University, Germany)** and **Tim Smith (CERN, Switzerland)**

This joint presentation covered the importance of Open Science for the future of scholarly research.

It explained how Zenodo works and how CERN is working to support Open Science.

The presentation also covered services for Open Science and the work of **OpenAIRE** within the context of the **European Commission Open Science Policy**.

“We are so pleased that we were able to make this happen” said Vincenzo Grillo, the Principal Investigator of Q-SORT. “OpenScience is a hot subject now and we are striving to position our project on the forefront. We are grateful to OpenAire Advance and CERN for their cooperation in this initiative”.

3.2 THE SIXTH INTERDISCIPLINARY TRAINING WEBINAR ON THE Q-SORT WEBSITE

A dedicated webpage for this webinar has been created on the Q-SORT website featuring:

1. the webinar;
2. a short description of the webinar thought for the general public;
3. a short bio of the speaker who offered the talk.

The link to the webpage is:

<http://www.qsort.eu/making-open-science-work-for-you/>

Making Open Science Work for You

Najla Retteberg, University of Gottingen (Germany) & Tim Smith, CERN (Switzerland)

02 July 2019, h. 4:30-5:15 PM CET

[Facebook Live: https://www.facebook.com/quantumsorter/](https://www.facebook.com/quantumsorter/)

This joint presentation will cover the importance of Open Science within research.

It will explain how [Zenodo](#) works and how [CERN](#) is working to support Open Science.

The presentation will also cover services for Open Science and the work of OpenAIRE within the context of European Commission Open Science policy.

About the Speakers

Najla Rettberg is the Scientific Manager of the [OpenAIRE Advance](#).

She is a librarian with extensive experience in open access, open science, e- infrastructures and digital preservation. An Arabist by training, she has also worked as a consultant for a range of institutions including King's College London, the Digital Preservation Coalition and OCLC.

Tim Smith is Head of Collaboration, Devices and Applications Group at [CERN](#), the European Particle Physics Laboratory.

Tim is an Open Science advocate leading initiatives at CERN and in the wider science community. He drove the launch of [CERN's Open Data Portal](#) to share [Large Hadron Collider](#) big data with the world, as well as the [Higgs Boson](#) webcast which shared its discovery live around the globe. He also instigated and nurtures [Zenodo](#) within the European Commission's [OpenAIRE](#) project as an open data service for world-wide science. Tim came to CERN at the end of the 80s, obtained a PhD in Particle Physics and performed research at the [Large Electron-Positron accelerator](#) for 10 years. He then joined the CERN IT Department to lead teams innovating in computing farm management and physics data management.

This is a Q-SORT outreach event in collaboration with [CERN](#) and [OpenAIRE](#)

Figure 1 - Screenshot of the sixth interdisciplinary training webinar page on the Q-SORT website

4 CONCLUSIONS

This is the sixth Interdisciplinary Training Webinar produced for Q-SORT by [QED](#), with additional support from partner Max Planck Institute for the Science of Light..

In the past few years we have seen a consistent rise in the popularity and value of webinars as an essential training, communication, and engagement tool.

The video of the webinar also offers a unique opportunity for engagement. The project will continue to promote on-demand webinars so that their audiences will get larger and more engaged, and spend more time watching webinars, both live and on-demand. In planning the next webinars we will evaluate the effectiveness of the previous ones and use this information as a guideline to help the Q-SORT consortium create, promote, and deliver even more successful webinars.

ANNEX 1: MAKING OPEN SCIENCE WORK FOR YOU

Making
Open Science
Work for You

International Conference on Quantum Imaging and Electron Beam Shaping,
Max Planck Institute for the Science of Light – 2019/07/02

CERN

Science for Peace

22 Member States
70 Countries
120 Nationalities
600 Universities

Collaboration
Fundamental Research

27km
-271.3°C
99.999999%

@TimSmithCH

The image features an aerial view of the LHC particle accelerator ring, which is highlighted in yellow. The ring is situated in a valley with mountains in the background. Various components of the accelerator are shown in different colors (purple, green, orange, red). The background is a blue sky with light clouds. The text is arranged in a structured layout with blue and light blue backgrounds for the text boxes.

Big Data !

40 million collisions /s
150 M sensors
Trigger 100 k events /s
Record 10 GB /s
Calibrate
Reconstruct

10 M lines of code
Analysis at 167 sites around world
320 PB

@TimSmithCH

Data Driven Science

1903

1989

@TimSmithCH

The Web Free Market

The collage features several overlapping web pages and interfaces. At the top left is a Google search page with the text 'high temperature superconductivity'. In the center is a GitHub page titled 'How developers work' with the subtitle 'Support your workflow with lightweight tools and features. Then work how you work best—we'll follow your lead.' To the right is a Bitbucket page with the heading 'Code, Manage, Collaborate' and the tagline 'Bitbucket is the Q1 solution for professional teams'. Further right is a Mendley Data advertisement: 'Put your research data online today with Mendley Data'. At the bottom left is a NASA website showing a '404' error message: 'The cosmic object you are looking for has disappeared beyond the event horizon.' In the bottom right of the collage is a 'Danger Zone' warning box with three options: 'Make this repository private', 'Transfer ownership', and 'Delete this repository'. To the right of the collage are logos for Blockbuster, Napster, and Nirvanix.

Share ≠ Publish ≠ Preserve

@TimSmithCH

CERN Open Data

<http://open.data.cern.ch>
<http://inveniosoftware.org>

@TimSmithCH

Analysis Preservation

<http://github.com/cernanalysispreservation>

@TimSmithCH

Enabling Open Science

@TimSmithCH

Open Research as a Service

- Dataset
- Software
- Article
- Image
- Video
- Poster
- Presentation
- Lesson

zenodo

Data files and electromagnetic simulation software used in the paper "Radar evidence of subglacial liquid water on Mars" By Crosetti et al. (2018)

899 views 3,145 downloads

OpenAIRE

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.1285179

<http://zenodo.org>

Liquid water 'lake' revealed on Mars

DOI 10.5281/zenodo.1285179

@TimSmithCH

Open Research as a Service

- Dataset
- Software
- Article
- Image
- Video
- Poster
- Presentation
- Lesson

The screenshot shows the Zenodo page for the software package 'eht-imaging: v1.1.0: Imaging interferometric data with regularized maximum likelihood'. The page includes a description, a list of authors, and a file browser showing various data files and scripts. A yellow arrow points from the file list to the article preview on the right.

The screenshot shows the article page for 'First M87 Event Horizon Telescope Results. IV. Imaging the Central Supermassive Black Hole' in The Astrophysical Journal Letters. The article is open access and includes a list of authors and a download button.

@TimSmithCH

Share ≠ Publish ≠ Preserve

The image illustrates the relationship between sharing, publishing, and preserving research. On the left, a Zenodo interface shows a 'Software' icon circled in red. In the center, a GitHub repository for 'Lasagne' is shown with a 'GitHub OpenAIRE' badge and a handshake icon. On the right, a Zenodo record for 'Lasagne: First release' is shown with yellow arrows pointing to the GitHub repository and the Zenodo record. Below is a 'Making Your Code Citable' guide from GitHub.

Towards Digital Age Scholarship

Preservation ↔ Reusability

<http://reana.io>

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Make Open Science a Reality

Findable
Accessible
Interoperable
Reusable

The Internet has fundamentally changed the practical and economic realities of distributing scientific knowledge and cultural heritage. For the first time ever, the Internet now offers the chance to constitute a global and interactive representation of human knowledge, including cultural heritage and the guarantee of worldwide access. We, the undersigned, feel obliged to address the challenges of the Internet as an emerging functional medium for distributing knowledge. Obviously, these developments will be able to significantly modify the nature of scientific habits as a

<https://openaccess.mpg.de/Berlin-Declaration>

DORA
<https://sfedora.org>

FORCE11
The Future of Research Communications and e-Scholarship

BOUCHOUT DECLARATION

<http://www.bouchoutdeclaration.org>

OPEN SCIENCE MOOC
RSC | 2025 | 4 ECTS
@TimSmithCH

SOFTWARE CITATION PRINCIPLES

... yet there is little support for its acknowledgement and citation.

EDD

<http://www.copdess.org/enabling-fair-data-project>

Thank You ! Questions ?

CERN Open Data
 <http://opendata.cern.ch>
 <http://github.com/cernopendata>
 cernopendata

CERN Analysis Preservation
 <http://analysispreservation.cern.ch>
 <http://github.com/cernanalysispreservation>
 analysispreserv

REANA
 <http://www.reanahub.io>
 <http://github.com/reanahub>
 reanahub

Invenio
 <http://inveniosoftware.org>
 <http://github.com/inveniosoftware>
 inveniosoftware

Zenodo
 <http://zenodo.org>
 <http://github.com/zenodo>
 zenodo_org

 <http://orcid.org/0000-0002-1567-7116>
 <http://cern.ch/Tim.Smith>

<http://openaire.eu>

@TimSmithCH

Najla Rettberg
University of Göttingen

OpenAIRE

How OpenAIRE can Support Open Science

OpenAIRE @QSort June 2019

This Presentation

OpenAIRE
The HOWs of Open Science: Our Services
European Open Science Cloud
Further Support

OpenAIRE @QSort June 2019

GEORG-AUGUST-UNIVERSITÄT
 GÖTTINGEN
 The University of Göttingen invites applications for the position of a
Professorship (W3 salary level, tenured)
 in „Clinical Psychology and Psychotherapy“
 The position will be available at the Georg-Elias-Müller-Institute of

Applications by advanced junior scientists, and by scientists from foreign countries are explicitly encouraged. The Institute aims for open, transparent and reproducible research, in line with the recent recommendations by the German Society of Psychology (Deutsche Gesellschaft für Psychologie, DGPs). Applicants are asked to outline how they have pursued these goals in the past, and how they plan to do so in the future.

The University of Göttingen intends to increase the proportion of women in research and teaching in areas where they are, so far, underrepresented and, hence, strongly encourages female scientists to apply. The University of Göttingen is an equal-opportunities employer. Furthermore, the university pursues the goal of hiring more disabled persons. Therefore, priority will be given to disabled persons with equivalent qualifications.

Germany: All documents should be sent as hard copies and, in addition, be put together as a single PDF file on a CD.

OpenAIRE @QSort June 2019

What does Open Science mean to you?

- Publishing a paper in an OA journal
- Deposit of a preprint* or final version in a repository
- Rethinking workflows, what tools enable Open Science
- [Checking out data repositories, how to cite data](#)
- **Making own research more reproducible**
- Engaging in replication studies
- ...

* Preprint = final author manuscript (before peer review), submitted or ready for submission to a publisher

OpenAIRE

open and **reproducible** science
scientific/scholarly **communication**
data infrastructure
social + technical links
service + data **interoperability**

Share, deposit and publish in OA

How to comply. What services to use.

Discover linked Open Research

Search for research results, projects, content providers and organizations

EXPLORE.
OpenAIRE Discovery service

Gather outputs. View progress and report. Monitor.

Services for researchers, project coordinators and research managers

Link your research results

Services for researchers, project coordinators and research managers

The How #1: OpenAIRE services & tools for H2020 compliance:

- ✓ Open Access depositing
- ✓ Storing research data in Zenodo
- ✓ Claiming publications and datasets
- ✓ Reporting research outputs
- ✓ Discover, analyse and access
- ✓ Helpdesk, training and support material

11

Open Access Policy

- The Grant Agreement states (29.2):

**“Ensure open access...
at the latest on publication, deposit a copy of
the published version or final peer-reviewed
manuscript in a repository for scientific
publications together with bibliographic
metadata providing the..grant number”**

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Open Research Data in H2020

1. Develop a [Data Management Plan \(DMP\)](#)
2. Deposit dataset in a [research data repository](#) together with the necessary information
3. Provide [open access](#) to research data, if possible

RESEARCH DATA - OPEN BY DEFAULT

Horizon 2020 grantees are required

- take measures to ensure open access to the data underlying their scientific publications
- provide open access to any other research data of their choice
- Horizon 2020 grantees are encouraged to also share datasets beyond publication

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- **primarily:** data needed to validate results in scientific publications
- **voluntarily:** any other curated and/or raw data, as specified in DMP

Degrees of data sharing

Participation in ORD Pilot does NOT mean you have to open up all data!

“As open as possible, as closed as necessary”

Aim to make your data FAIR

EC's Guidelines on FAIR Data Management in Horizon 2020

From 'Expert Four Guide on Data Management' by CESSDA, ERIC, GBVSA, OpenAIRE @QSort, June 2019

How #2: Helping you to upload

The screenshot shows the OpenAIRE EXPLORE interface. The top navigation bar includes 'EXPLORE', 'PROVIDE', 'CONNECT', 'MONITOR', and 'DEVELOP'. Below the navigation, there are links for 'SEARCH', 'SHARE', 'LINK', 'CONTENT PROVIDERS', and 'FERRO PRINCE'. The main content area is divided into two sections:

- Share Publications:** This section prompts users to see if their institution has a repository. It features a search bar with a 'Locate' button and a list of content providers including SIGCOMM (ACM SIGCOMM), Fundação Calouste Gulbenkian (FCG-IGC), IGC/Advanced Supercomputers, Inc., BigChange Apps Limited, Biocat@rs Ltd (IGC), INSTITUT GEOLÒGIC DE CATALUNYA (IGC), and IGC CHAMP PRO EUROPA SL (IGSCHAMP PRO EUROPA SL). A map shows the location of the selected provider. A callout box says 'Deposit your Publications in Europe!'. A URL is provided: <https://explore.openaire.eu/participate/deposit-publications>.
- Share Research Data:** This section also prompts users to see if their institution has a repository. It includes a search bar for domain-specific repositories with a 'Search' button. The footer of this section reads 'OpenAIRE @QSort June 2019'.

Share, deposit and publish in OA
 How to comply. What services to use.

Discover linked Open Research
 Search for research results, projects, content providers and organizations
 EXPLORE. OpenAIRE Discovery service

Gather outputs. View progress and report. Monitor.
 Services for researchers, project coordinators and research managers

Link your research results
 Services for researchers, project coordinators and research managers

The How #4: Research Community Dashboard

OpenAIRE CONNECT

A Gateway to the future of your Community

Turn Open Science into Practice. It takes your open and linked research outcomes. A service customized to your needs.

LEARN HOW

Our mission for an Open and FAIR science

- A Virtual Research Environment**
An over-lying platform making it easy to share, link, disseminate and monitor all your publications, data, software, methods, in one place.
 - Access to OpenAIRE resources
 - Moderated, free web training
 - Cross platform search
- Open Science in action**
A time saving bundle of services for researchers to effortlessly practice open science. An integral part of the European Open Science Cloud.
 - Use of OpenAIRE Guidelines
 - 2020 via Zenodo
 - ORCID Single Sign-On
- Customized to your needs**
A Gateway with your own brand, rules for aggregation, HTML & data mining and presentation. Run by you via a simple, yet powerful, backend administration tool.
 - Access control
 - Analytics, rich set of indicators
 - Look & feel to match your brand

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Helping you Publish, Share, Discover

AGINFRA

Agricultural and Food Sciences
AGINFRA

The scope of this community is to provide access to publications, research data, projects and software that are related to agricultural and food sciences.

Subscribe

313,554	19,381	3,767	85,042	78	6
publications	research data	software	datasets	journals	journals in production

Most recent statistics

Publications

Publications through the years

Publications by access mode

Open Access 80.7% (276,884)

OpenAIRE 14.1% (45,166)

Restricted 3.2% (10,110)

embargo 1.2% (3,744)

ORCID

OpenAIRE

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Research Communities already on board

SDSN GREECE

Sustainable and Development S Network

Neuroinformati

Is there interest from you as a Physics Community?

.....All your Outputs in One Place
....Yours to moderate
....Track impact

OpenAIRE @QSort June 2019

Blowing on the fire of Open Science

Facilitate Research Communities adoption of **Open Science publishing** principles by supporting artefact publishing tools as-a-Service

Facilitate Collaborative curation of a community-specific research domain

The How #5: Services for RDM

The collage features three overlapping screenshots of RDM services. On the left is the Zenodo logo with the tagline 'Research. Share.' Below it is the OpenAIRE logo and the European Union flag. In the center is the easyDMP dashboard, showing a navigation bar with 'Data Management Plans', 'PROJECTS', 'PLANS', and 'SERVICES'. It displays three statistics: '9 Data Plans', '14 Data Objects', and '24 Data Objects'. On the right is the Amnesia website, with a navigation menu including 'Home', 'Get Amnesia!', 'What is Amnesia?', 'Documentation', 'On-line version', and 'About'. The main heading is 'Amnesia', followed by a description: 'Amnesia is a data anonymization tool, that allows to remove identifying information from data. Amnesia not only removes direct identifiers like names, SSNs etc but also transforms secondary identifiers like birth date and zip code so that individuals cannot be identified in the data. Amnesia supports k-anonymity and k'-anonymity.' The footer of the Amnesia page reads 'OpenAIRE @QSort June 2019'.

OpenAIRE: A pillar in EOSC

OpenAIRE @QSort June 2019

EOSC at a glance

The role of the EOSC is to ensure that **European scientists reap the full benefits of data-driven science**, by offering:

“1.7 million European researchers and 70 million professionals in science and technology a virtual environment with free at the point of use, open and seamless services for storage, management, analysis and re-use of research data, across borders and scientific disciplines”

[2016 Communication on the “European Cloud Initiative”](#)

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Key characteristics

- ❑ **Trusted and open virtual environment** with seamless access to services (with highest TRLs) addressing the whole research
 - ❑ Federating core services to federate and connect existing or planned RIs
 - ❑ Services to make data FAIR, store them, ensure their long-term preservation
 - ❑ Services to find, access, combine, analyse and process data
- ❑ **Open, transparent, rule of law based**: no lock-in by individual service providers, data portability, IPR, cloud security...
- ❑ **Adaptively user-oriented** and inclusive (across borders and disciplines)
- ❑ Governed by a minimal set of **Rules of Participation**
- ❑ Steered by an **inclusive governance structure**

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The How #6: Supporting you in OS

Distributed and hierarchical training

National / research infras, organizations → Researchers

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Get in touch: we are here to help!
Open Access representatives and liaisons in all EU member states

Outreach

Support

Training

Policy

www.openaire.eu/contact-roads OpenAIRE © Q-Sort June 2019

Thank you!

- www.openaire.eu
- [@openaire_eu](https://twitter.com/openaire_eu)
- facebook.com/groups/openaire
- nrettbe@gwdg.de

ANNEX 2: ABBREVIATIONS

SHORT NAME OF PARTICIPANTS

Partner	Country	Short Name
National Research Council (Project scientific coordinator)	Italy	CNR
Forschungszentrum Jülich, Ernst Ruska-Centre for Microscopy and Spectroscopy with Electrons	Germany	FZJ
FEI - Thermo Fisher Scientific	The Netherlands	FEI
The Max Planck Institute for the Science of Light	Germany	MPI
University of Glasgow, Department of Physics and Astronomy	United Kingdom	UG
QED Film & Stage Productions Ltd.	United Kingdom	QED
University of Modena and Reggio Emilia, Department of Physics, Informatics, and Mathematics	Italy	UMR
Maastricht University, Maastricht MultiModal Molecular Imaging Institute	The Netherlands	MU

LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS

Consortium Agreement	CA
Description of Action	DoA
Description of Work	DoW
European Commission	EC
Grant Agreement	GA
Kick-off Meeting	KoM
Project Management Board	PMB
Work Package	WP
Work Package Leader	WPL